

Potentiometric Determination of Stability Constants of Rare-earth Complexes with α -Carboxy- β -methyltropolone

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Stability constants of 1:1, 1:2, and 1:3 complexes of rare-earths with α -carboxy- β -methyltropolone have been determined by potentiometric method in 0.2*M* sodium perchlorate medium. The values of stability constants increase with increasing atomic number of the rare-earth cation.

During the studies on rare-earth complexes in recent years, stability constants of the complexes in many cases with a particular ligand have been found to increase with increasing atomic number of the rare-earth cation¹.

Dyrsson² has carried out extensive investigations on solvent extraction of rare-earth complexes with β -isopropyltropolone, but no work appears to have been done to find out the stability constants of the various complexes formed with tropolones. In the present work, the stability constants of 1:1, 1:2, and 1:3 complexes of rare-earths with α -carboxy- β -methyltropolone have been determined by *pH* titrations.

EXPERIMENTAL

A Metrohm *pH*-meter, model E-350, was used for measurement of *pH*. α -carboxy- β -methyltropolone was prepared by the method of Crow *et al.*³ Lanthanum nitrate, cerous nitrate, praseodymium nitrate, neodymium nitrate, and samarium nitrate, all of analytical reagent grade, were obtained from Atomic Energy Establishment, Trombay, Bombay. Solutions of gadolinium, dysprosium, holmium, erbium, ytterbium, lutetium and yttrium were prepared by dissolving the corresponding oxides (99.9% pure) obtained from Johnson-Matthey, London, in dilute nitric acid added dropwise. All solutions were standardised gravimetrically. The amount of free nitric acid in metal nitrate solutions was determined potentiometrically by using Gran's method. The metal nitrate solutions obtained from Atomic Energy Establishment did not contain any free acid; in other cases the concentration of free nitric acid found was allowed for in the calculations. Sodium perchlorate (L.R. B.D.H.) was added to all solutions to keep the ionic strength constant (0.2*M*). All solutions were prepared in double-distilled water. Values of *pH* were converted to concentration values using the correction factor—0.08 *pH* unit found for a dilute solution of perchloric acid (containing 0.2*M* sodium perchlorate). All measurements were carried out at 25°±1°.

1. Moeller *et al.*, *Chem. Rev.*, 1965, 63, 1.
2. *Trans. Royal Inst. Tech.*, Stockholm, 1962, No. 188.
3. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 3705.

Stability Constants: The determination of stability constants was carried out using Bjerrum-Calvin titration technique. The following solutions (total vol. 25 ml.) were titrated against $N/20$ -NaOH and the titration curves were plotted:

- (1) 2 ml. of $M/20$ perchloric acid+2.5 ml. of $2M$ sodium perchlorate+20.5 ml. water.
- (2) 2 ml. of $M/20$ perchloric acid+2.5 ml. of $2M$ sodium perchlorate+10 ml. of $M/100$ ligand+10.5 ml. water.
- (3) 2 ml. of $M/20$ perchloric acid+2.5 ml. of $2M$ sodium perchlorate+10 ml. of $M/100$ ligand+1.0 ml. $M/50$ metal ion+9.5 ml. water.

FIG. 1. Formation curves of rare-earth complexes with α -carboxy- β -methyltropolone

From titration curves (1) and (2), $\bar{n}_H$ values at different pH values were determined. From these values, pK_{a_1} and pK_{a_2} were calculated and found to be 2.48 and 7.45. Titration

curves (2) and (3) almost coincide at higher pH values (above 9.5) at which the reagent is completely ionised. This shows that the metal complexes are not hydrolysed even at high pH values. From curves (2) and (3), $\bar{n}$ and pL values at various pHs have been calculated and plotted (Fig. 1). From these plots, approximate values of $\log K_n$ were obtained at $\bar{n} = n - \frac{1}{2}$. $\bar{n}$ values lower than 1 were not obtained in case of some of the strongly complexing cations. In such cases, approximate values of $\frac{1}{2} (\log K_1, \log K_n)$ were obtained at pL values when $\bar{n} = 1$. Knowing the approximate value of $\log K_n$ at $\bar{n} = 1.5$, the values of $\log K_1$ could thus be calculated. The uncertainty in values of $\log K_1$ is greater in such cases. The approximate values, thus obtained, were refined by substitution in the following equation and recalculation⁴:

$$\log K_1 = -\log [L] + \log \frac{\sum_{n=1}^{i-1} (\bar{n} - n) \beta_n [L]^n}{\sum_{i=1}^N (n - \bar{n}) \beta_n K_1^{i-1} [L]^{n-1}}$$

where $[L]$ is the free ligand concentration, the rest of the terms have their usual significance.

The values of stability constants obtained are recorded in Table I. The uncertainty in the values of $\log K$ is of the order of ± 0.1 .

TABLE I

Metal ion	$\log K_1$	$\log K_2$	$\log \beta_2$	$\log K_3$	$\log \beta_3$
Lanthanum	7.20	5.56	12.76	3.40	16.16
Cerium (III)	7.42	5.72	13.14	3.34	16.48
Praseodymium	7.74	5.96	13.70	3.56	17.26
Neodymium	7.76	6.04	13.80	3.70	17.50
Samarium	7.98	6.42	14.40	3.78	18.18
Gadolinium	8.02	6.38	14.40	3.82	18.22
Dysprosium	8.28	6.78	15.06	4.00	19.06
Holmium	8.24	6.76	15.00	3.98	18.98
Erbium	8.35	6.85	15.20	4.18	19.38
Ytterbium	8.60	7.00	15.60	4.42	20.02
Lutetium	8.64	7.06	15.70	4.60	20.30
Yttrium	8.26	6.62	14.88	3.96	18.84

Table I shows that the values of $\log K_1$, $\log K_2$, and $\log K_3$ all increase with decrease in atomic radius and a break in all these values is obtained at gadolinium which has also been observed by a number of other workers¹.